

DEPENDENCE OF FRACTURE BEHAVIORS ON SiC_p SIZE OF Al MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The present paper was conducted to study the fracture behaviors of three kinds of silicon carbide (SiC) particulate reinforced pure aluminum metal matrix composites. The results indicated that the fracture toughness depends on the SiC particle size of reinforcement of the composite. When the particle size is relatively small, the fracture toughness will increase as the particle size increases; whereas the toughness decreases with increasing the particle size when the size is very large. The experimental results were discussed based on our recent model on metal matrix composites. Behaviors of acoustic emission and observations of scanning electron microscopy also proved the explanation.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites which are formed by reinforcing metallic materials with high strength ceramic phases exhibit some advantages over the matrix metals, such as high specific strength, modulus and stiffness[1]. With the development of metal matrix composites and their high performance engineering applications in aerospace, aircraft and automobile industries, their mechanical properties and fracture behaviors become critical in design and in service. However, metal matrix composites, as a whole, are only in the preliminary stages of development and there have been very limited engineering applications since significant problems remain unclear[1,2]. The lowered fracture toughness of the composite, when compared with the corresponding wrought matrix metals, is the major drawback of the metal matrix composite.

Many factors influence the fracture toughness of metal matrix composites[3-12], such as the volume fraction of reinforcements, size and distribution of reinforcements, matrix composition and heat treatment, etc. Among these factors, the effect of the reinforcement size on the fracture toughness was investigated limitedly and some results reported in the literature could not coincide with each other. Kamat *etal*[5], Downes *etal*[9] and Zhao and Tuler[10] showed that the fracture toughness increased with increasing the particle size of the reinforcement. Flom and Arsenault[4], however, turned out the contrary viewpoint that the fracture toughness was relatively constant in spite of the increase of reinforcement size. The latter result was also consistent with Roebuck and Lord's discussion[6].

The research reported here was conducted to investigate the fracture toughness of three kinds of SiC particulate reinforced pure aluminum metal matrix composite. During the testing, acoustic emission technique was applied to monitor the microfractural processes of the composite. Fracture surface produced by three-point bending specimens was also examined using the scanning electron microscopy. The results indicated that the fracture toughness values did not show the monotonic change as the size of reinforcement increased or decreased. The microfractural mechanism of the composite was discussed with both experimental and theoretical methods.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The commercially pure aluminum (Al-0.15Fe-0.14Si-0.014Cu, wt%) powders ($14\mu\text{m}$) were employed as the matrix metal and the α -SiC particulates with a mean size of $4\mu\text{m}$, $12\mu\text{m}$ and $43\mu\text{m}$ were used as the reinforcements, respectively. The composite containing 20vol.% SiC particulates was produced by using a powder metallurgy route involving blending, hot pressing and hot rolling.

The pure mode I fracture toughness test specimen is $5\times 10\times 60\text{mm}^3$, as shown in Fig.1. It is based on the standard three-point bending specimen design recommended by ASTM E-813. Because of the difficulty of precracking metal matrix composites by fatigue, notch of the root radius $50\mu\text{m}$ cut via an electro-sparkle machine was used instead of the fatigue precrack. The fracture toughness was found[11,12] to attain a limiting minimum value with a notch root radius of $80\mu\text{m}$ in particulate reinforced aluminum matrix composites. Fracture toughness testing was performed on an EHF-FB05-4LA Shimadzu testing machine at a constant cross-head speed of $5\mu\text{m/s}$. During the toughness testing, the acoustic emission equipment (LOCAN AT, PAC Co.) was used to monitor the microfracture processes of the composite. Finally, fractographic observation was carried out in a Cambridge S360 scanning electron microscopy in order to identify the failure mechanism.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of fracture toughness test specimen

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental data of fracture toughness J_{Ic} for the three kinds of the composite were shown in Fig.2. The results indicated that the fracture toughness depended on the SiC particle size of reinforcement of the composite. However, the toughness did not change monotonically as the size of SiC particle increased. When SiC particle size increased from $4\mu\text{m}$ to $12\mu\text{m}$, the fracture toughness increased, which was in agreement with the data of References [5], [9] and [10].

Figure 2. Effect of SiC size on fracture toughness of SiCp/Al composites

Hahn and Rosenfield[13] analyzed the fracture toughness data obtained by a variety of investigators, and in accordance with the model proposed by Rice and Johnson[14], they proposed that the toughness J_{IC} could be written as

$$J_{IC} = 2\sigma\left(\frac{\pi}{6}\right)^{1/3}d(1-\nu^2)V_f^{-1/3} \quad (1)$$

where d was the particle size, V_f the volume fraction of particle, ν the Poisson's ratio and σ the strength of the material. From the above equation, it was shown that the toughness of the composite increased as the particle size increased under the condition of constant V_f . The calculated data[2] from Eqn.(1) were in accordance with our experimental results for the range of particle size changing from 4µm to 12µm (Fig.2).

However, a contrary result was derived as the particle size increased to 43µm, which was inconsistent with Hahn-Rosenfield theory. This discrepancy could be explained by our recent model on metal matrix composites[15], which showed that when the particle size was relatively small, it could be impossible for crack of reinforcement particles to propagate very much because in this case the matrix stress would exceed the yield strength. Thus, cracking of the composite occurred in the matrix rather than the reinforcement itself, and the reinforcement particles could hinder the propagation of matrix crack and make the crack deflecting. This kind of shielding effect would lead to the increase of fracture toughness. Nevertheless, when the particle size of reinforcement was very large, the overall fracture processes could be dominated by the cracking of reinforcement particles[15], which accelerated the coalescence between the main crack and microcrack. So, the fracture toughness decreased. Flom and Arsenault[4] also reported the decrease of fracture toughness once the reinforcement size was very large.

Behaviors of acoustic emission and observations of scanning electron microscopy also proved the above explanation. It was shown from Fig.3 that acoustic emission signals were more and more active as the particle size increased, which indicated that more and more particles of the composite fractured. Morphology of fracture surface of the composite revealed (Fig.4) that the fracture occurred by a locally ductile mechanism which was controlled by void nucleation, growth and coalescence in the matrix when the particle size was relatively small; whereas much cleavage fracture of particles occurred in the case of the coarse particle reinforced composite.

Figure 3. Energy dissipation versus loading time of acoustic emission
(a) $4\mu\text{m SiCp/Al}$, (b) $12\mu\text{m SiCp/Al}$ and (c) $43\mu\text{m SiCp/Al}$

Figure 4. SEM fractograph of fracture surfaces of 4 μ m(a), 12 μ m(b) and 43 μ m(c) average size SiCp reinforced Al composites

CONCLUSIONS

From the data generated from the SiCp/Al composite in this investigation some conclusions can be drawn. The fracture toughness depends on the particulate size of reinforcement of the composite. When the particle size is relatively small, the fracture toughness will increase as the particle size increases; whereas the toughness decreases with increasing the particle size when the size is very large.

Acknowledgements: The authors would like to express their acknowledgements to the supports by the National High-Tech Project under Grant No. 863715121002 and the National Natural Science Foundation of China under Grant No. 59281004.

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